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PhD по медицинским наукам, Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
PhD in Medical Sciences,
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Indiaminova Gulrux Nuriddinova
Samarqand tibbiyot universiteti
Samarqand, O'zbekiston

Azizova Suman Abduraxmonovna
Samarqand tibbiyot universiteti
Samarqand, O'zbekiston

О'TKIR RESPIRATOR INFEKSIYALAR VA HOMILADORLIK, GEMOSTAZ TIZIMIGA TA'SIRI (ADABIYOT TAHLILII)

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Индиаминова Гульрух Нуриддинова
Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет
Самарканд, Узбекистан

Азизова Суман Абдурахмоновна
Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет
Самарканд, Узбекистан

ОСТРЫЕ РЕСПИРАТОРНЫЕ ИНФЕКЦИИ И БЕРЕМЕННОСТЬ, ВЛИЯНИЕ НА СИСТЕМУ ГЕМОСТАЗА (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)

Indiaminova Gulrux Nuriddinova
Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Azizova Suman Abduraxmonovna
Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan

ACUTE RESPIRATORY INFECTIONS AND PREGNANCY, INFLUENCE ON THE HEMOSTASIS SYSTEM (LITERATURE REVIEW)

2019-yil oxirida Xitoyning Xubey provinsiyasidagi Uxan shahrida yangi turdagi koronavirus aniqlanib, u pnevmoniya holatlarining jadal sur'atlarda yuzaga kelishiga sabab bo'ldi [13]. Virus tez tarqalib, dastlab Xitoyda, so'ngra butun dunyo bo'ylab epidemiya avj olishiga olib keldi. 2020-yil fevral oyida Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti (JSST) bu kasallikni COVID-19 deb atadi. COVID-19 yoki og'ir darajali o'tkir respirator sindromga sabab bo'luvchi virus SARS-CoV-2 nomi bilan yuritiladi [15, 29].

Ushbu virus bilan kasallanish natijasida homilador ayollarda og'ir pnevmoniya rivojlanish ehtimoli yuqori bo'lib, ularning 22–30% reanimatsiya va intensiv terapiya bo'limlariga yotqiziladi. 15–26% holatlarda respirator distress sindromi rivojlanishi mumkin. Kasalxonaga yotqizilgan homilador ayollar orasida o'lim holati 4–15% ni tashkil etishi mumkin. Olingan ma'lumotlarga qaraganda o'lim holatining umumiy koeffitsienti 1% ni tashkil etdi [19].

Bu kasallikning inkubatsiya davri 2 kundan 14 kungacha bo'lib, o'rtacha 5–7 kuni tashkil etadi [22]. Umumpopulyatsiya orasida klinik belgilar yengil shakldan tortib og'ir kritik holatlargacha o'zgarishi mumkin. Ammo aksariyat holatlarda kasallik og'ir shaklda kechmaydi [31, 34].

JSST va CDC (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention) ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, COVID-19 bilan kasallangan bemorlar quyidagi belgilarga ega bo'lishi mumkin [25]:

- Yengil shakl: 81% holatlarda yengil pnevmoniya yoki umuman pnevmoniyasiz kechadi.

- Og'ir shakl: 14% bemorlarda nafas qisilishi, gipoksiya va o'pka to'qimasining 50% dan ortiq qismining zararlanish kuzatiladi.

- Kritik shakl: 5% holatda nafas yetishmovchiligi, shok, poliorgan yetishmovchiligi kuzatiladi.

- O'lim darajasi: o'rtacha 2,3% ni tashkil qildi, ammo kritik holatda bo'lmagan bemorlarda o'lim kuzatilmagan.

Klinik kechishi. Umumpopulyatsiyada COVID-19 ning eng ko'p uchraydigan jiddiy klinik belgilardan biri bu pnevmoniya hisoblanadi, va bu birinchi o'rinda tana haroratining ko'tarilishi, yo'tal, nafas qisishi hamda o'pkalarda bilateral infiltratlar bilan namoyon bo'ladi. COVID-19 ning boshqa virusli respirator infeksiyalardan farqli spetsifik klinik belgilari aniqlanmadi.

COVID-19 bilan kasallangan homilador ayollarda odatda quyidagi simptomlar kuzatiladi: isitma (99% holatlarda), holsizlik (70%), quruq yo'tal (59%), ishtaha yo'qolishi (40%), mushak og'rig'i (35%), balg'am

ajralishi (27%), kam uchraydigan belgilarga bosh og'rig'i, tomoq og'rig'i, burun bitishi va rinoreya kiradi. Ayrim bemorlar nafas olish tizimi tomonidan namoyon bo'ladigan simptomlardan tashqari oshqozon-ichak traktining buzilishlari bilan bog'liq shikoyatlarni bildirishi mumkin (masalan, ko'ngil aynishi va diareya) [8]. Ba'zi holatlarda esa yuqoridagi klinik simptomatikaga es-xushining karaxtligi (9%), bosh og'rig'i (8%), qon aralash qayt qilish (5%) va yurak urib ketishi (11%) belgilar qo'shilishi mumkin [11].

Kasallikning simptomlarsiz kechadigan turi haqida ham ma'lumotlar mavjud, ammo kasallikning bu turning uchrash chastotasi aniq bo'lmagan qolmoqda [9].

Umumpopulyatsiyadagi boshqa bemorlar singari homilador ayollar ham yengil yoki o'rta darajadagi gripp yoki o'tkir respirator kasalliklarga o'xshash simptomlar bilan shifokorga murojaat qilishadi. Ular, ayniqsa, og'ir pnevmoniya va gipoksiya rivojlanish xavfi yuqori bo'lganligi sababli sinchkovlik bilan nazorat qilinishi lozim.

Pnevmoniyaning bu turi qariyalarda, qandli diabet, onkologik kasalliklar, o'pka kasalliklari bilan kasallangan immunodefitsit holatidagi bemorlarda ko'proq uchraydi, shuningdek homiladorlarda ham ehtiyotkorlikni talab etadi. Homiladorlar uchun absolyut xavf darajasi sezilarli bo'lmasa ham kasallikning og'ir darajasini o'z vaqtida tashxislash va talab etiladigan tibbiy yordam va davolash muolajalarini kechiktirmasdan o'z vaqtida amalga oshirish lozim [5, 21].

COVID-19 tashxisi klinik simptomlar va laboratoriya natijalariga asoslangan holda qo'yiladi. Asosiy diagnostik belgilar: isitma, tana haroratining ko'tarilishi, umumiy holsizlik, mushak og'rig'i, quruq yo'tal, nafas qisishi. Ba'zan burun bitishi, rinit, tomoq og'rig'i, qon tupurish, diareya kabi simptomlar ham kuzatilishi mumkin. Qon tahlilida kasallikning boshlang'ich bosqichlarida leykotsitlar soni normada yoki biroz kamayishi mumkin, limfopeniya kuzatilishi ham mumkin. C-reaktiv oqsil (CRP) ning yuqoriligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Ayrim bemorlarda trombositopeniya, jigar fermentlari va kreatin fosfokinaza miqdorining oshishi kuzatiladi [23].

Virusli pnevmoniya tashxisini tasdiqlash yoki inkor qilish uchun eng qimmatli instrumental tekshirish usullaridan biri ko'krak qafasining kontrastsiz kompyuter tomografiyasi (KT) hisoblanadi. Bu tekshirish usulini barcha shubhali holatlarda amalga oshirish lozim, chunki bunda homila uchun xavf darajasi minimal hisoblanadi. COVID-19 pnevmoniyasini tashxislashda KT tekshiruvining sezuvchanligi ya'ni informativligi polimeraz zanjirli reaksiya (PZR) usulidan ham yuqori (98% ga nisbatan 71%) ekanligi tasdiqlangan [18]. Homiladorlarda COVID-19 bo'lgan holatlarning ko'pchiligida virusli pnevmoniyaning radiologik belgilari aniqlanadi. Virusli pnevmoniyaning asosiy belgisi "muzli oyna" ko'rinishidagi infiltratning bo'lishi hisoblanadi.

COVID-19 ning laborator tashxislanishi uchun PZR usuli qo'llaniladi. Laborator tekshirish usullarini o'tkazish uchun asosiy materiallar bu burun-halqum va/yoki og'iz-halqumdan olingan surtma xizmat qiladi [10, 14]. A. D. Sutton et al., (2020) tomonidan Nyu-Yorkda o'tkazilgan tadqiqot davomida 33 nafar homiladorlikning oxirgi muddatlarida bo'lgan ayollar SARS-CoV-2 virusi bilan infitsirlanganligi aniqlandi, asosan ularning 29 nafarida kasallikning yaqqol klinik simptomatikasi kuzatilmadi [17, 30].

Shunday qilib, homiladorlik davrida SARS-CoV-2 virusi bilan infitsirlangan homiladorlarda COVID-19 ning klinik kechishi homilador bo'lmagan ayollardan deyarli farq qilmaydi va tana haroratining ko'tarilishi, qiyin ajraluvchi balg'am bilan yo'tal, ko'krak qafasida og'riq, ba'zida esa diareya belgilari bilan namoyon bo'ladi. Qonning umumiy taxlilida limfopeniya, S reaktiv oqsil (SRO), aspartate aminotransferaza (AST), alanine aminotransferaza (ALT) ko'rsatkichlarining ortishi kuzatiladi. Nurli diagnostika usullaridan foydalanilganda bir tomonlama yoki ikki tomonlama "muzli oyna" tipidagi infiltrate o'choqlari aniqlanishi mumkin, bu ham homilador bo'lmaganlardan farq qilmaydi.

COVID-19 bo'lgan homiladorlarda gemostaz tizimi. COVID-19 ning og'ir turlarida koagulyatsiyaning o'zgarishi asosan D-dimer va fibrinogen darajasining ortishi bilan xarakterlanadi, bu esa tromboz va ayniqsa o'pka arteriyalarining tromboemboliyasi xavfini oshirishi mumkin. "COVID-19 kasalligining kechishi qonning tomir ichida ivish jarayoniga bevosita bog'liq" – deb gemostazologiya yo'nalishida yetakchi akusher-ginekolog A.D. Makatsariya o'z intervyusida

ta'kidlaydi [11]. COVID-19 birinchi o'rinda pastki nafas yo'llarining infitsirlanishini chaqirib, yo'tal, isitma, nafas yetishmasligi va letargiya bilan namoyon bo'lishiga qaramasdan, yurak-qon tomir va immune tizimi tomonidan ham bir yoki bir nechta organlarning yetishmovchiligi, disseminirlangan tomir ichi qon ivishi sindromi (DVS) kabi asoratlar ham kuzatilishi mumkin [4]. Homilador ayollarning koagulyatsion tizimiga virusning ta'siri haqidagi ma'lumotlar yetarli emas, shu qatorda koronavirusning boshqa shtammlari – og'ir o'tkir respirator sindrom (SARS) va yaqin sharq respirator sindromi (MERS) bilan infitsirlangan ayollarda ham qon ivish tizimining o'zgarishlari kuzatiladi [6, 20, 32]. COVID-19 sababli Virxov uchligining buzilishi hamda homiladorlik davridagi normal fiziologik o'zgarishlar ayol organizmida arterial, venoz va platsental tromblar hosil bo'lish xavfini oshiradi, bu holatni antitrombotik farmakologik dori vositalari, shuningdek virusga qarshi, yallig'lanishga qarshi dori vositalar yordamida nazorat qilib borish mumkin.

Homiladorlik davridagi tabiiy fiziologik o'zgarishlarning o'zi ham homilador ayollar qonida giperkoagulyatsiya holatini keltirib chiqaradi. Bu esa o'z navbatida qon ivish tizimi omillari ko'rsatkichlarining (VII, VIII va X omil, Villebrand omili (vWF), D-dimer, C-reaktiv oqsil va fibrinogen) ortishiga olib keladi. Shu bilan birga fibrinoliz jarayoni ingibitorlarining miqdori ham ortadi. Shuningdek, Protrombin vaqtining (PV) uzayishi va/yoki faollashgan qisman tromboplastin vaqtining (AChTV) uzayishi, hamda C oqsili darajasining va faollashgan C oqsiliga nisbatan turg'unlikning pasayishi kuzatiladi, bu holat ayniqsa homiladorlikning ikkinchi va uchinchi trimestrlarida kuchayadi, natijada omillar koagulyatsiyani ingibirlay olmaydi. Homilador ayollar organizmida yuz beradigan anatomic o'zgarishlar ham muhim ahamiyatga ega, masalan, homiladorlik hisobiga kattalashgan bachadonning chanoq venalarini bosishi hisobiga oyoqlarda qon aylanishining buzilishi sodir bo'lishi mumkin. Bu esa o'z navbatida venoz qon dimlanishi natijasida qon laxtalarining – tromblarning hosil bo'lishiga olib keladi [6, 27]. Shuning uchun, COVID-19 tashxisi bilan gospitalizatsiya qilingan bemorlarda trombositlar sonini, prothrombin vaqtini va/yoki faollashgan qisman tromboplastin vaqtini, D-dimer va fibrinogen miqdorini qat'iy nazorat qilib borish tavsiya qilinadi.

O'tkir respirator viruslarning endothelial hujayralarga invazyasi endothelial hujayralarning zararlanishiga, fibrinolitik funksiyasining buzilishiga hamda tromblar hosil bo'lishiga sabab bo'ladi, buning natijasida esa vWF omilining ko'p miqdorda ajralishi kuzatiladi [3, 17]. Endoteliy qavatining himoya funksiyasining yo'qotilishi qon laxtalarini eritish tizimining suayishiga sabab bo'ladi, bunda giperkoagulyatsiya holati yanada kuchayishi yuz beradi. Shu bilan birga, COVID-19 kasalligida tomir ichida fibrin yig'ilishi ham kuchayadi, buning natijasida qonning yopishqoqliq ortadi va qon aylanishining sekinlashishi yuzaga keladi. Keltirilgan ma'lumotlarning barchasi shuni tasdiqlaydiki, COVID-19 tromblar hosil bo'lishi va tromboemboliya rivojlanishi uchun xavf omili sifatida xizmat qilishi mumkin [4, 7].

COVID-19 bilan kasallangan bemorlar qonida neytrofiliya, leykositoz, prothrombin vaqtining uzayishi hamda interleykinlar: IL-6 va IL-8 miqdorining ortishi, D-dimer darajasining oshishi kuzatiladi. Neytrofillarning limfotsitlarga nisbati (NLR) kasallikning kelajakda qanday kechishi haqidagi prognostic omil sifatida xizmat qilishi mumkin (NLR <3,13 bo'lsa xavf darajasi past, ≥3,13 bo'lsa xavf darajasi yuqori hisoblanadi) [12, 24]. Koronavirus infeksiyasi bilan bog'liq koagulopatiya kasallikning boshlang'ich bosqichlarida DVS-sindrom belgilarisiz giperkoagulyatsiya rivojlanishi bilan xarakterlanadi. D-dimer ko'rsatkichining ortishi, trombositlar miqdorining biroz kamayishi (trombositlar sonining <150*10⁹/l bo'lishi 70-95% bemorlarda kuzatiladi), PV ning biroz uzayishi, fibrinogen ("yallig'lanishning o'tkir fazasi oqsili") miqdorining ortishi sodir bo'lishi mumkin. Shu bilan birga antitrombin III konsentratsiyasi 80% gacha pasayishi mumkin, C oqsilining konsentratsiyasida esa deyarli o'zgarish kuzatilmaydi [5, 26].

Koronavirus infeksiyasi tomonidan chaqirilgan pnevmoniyalarda koagulopatiya kuzatilganida fibrin va trombositlar parchalanishining odatiy belgilari kuzatilmaydi. Shuningdek, mikroangiopatoya belgilari ham bo'lmaydi [12, 14].

Agarda infeksiyon jarayonining og'ir turdagi kechishi kuzatilsa, qon ivish tizimining ikkilamchi faollashuvi sodir bo'ladi va antikoagulyatsion tizim endogen mexanizmining bu jarayon bilan kurashishga kuchi yetmaydi, generalizatsiyalashgan o'tkir yallig'lanish reaksiyasi esa qon tomirlar endoteliyasining shikastlanishiga olib keladi, buning natijasida esa o'tkir DVS-sindrom, gipoksiya, to'qimalar ishemiyasi, hayotiy muhim organlar funksiyasining buzilishlari, oqibatda poliorgan yetishmovchilik rivojlanishiga olib keladi [1, 24]. Yangi turdagi koronavirus infeksiyasi bilan kasallanib, so'ngra tuzalganlar orasida disseminirlangan tomir ichi qon ivish sindromi faqatgina 0,6% holatlarda aniqlangan, bu kasallik natijasida o'gan bemorlar orasida esa bu sindrom 71,4% holatlarda kuzatilgan [18]. V. Bitsadze va hammualiflar (2020) koronavirus infeksiyasi bilan kasallanish jarayonida rivojlangan DVS-sindromning patogenezini o'rgandi [2, 5, 28]. Bu bir-biri bilan uzviy bog'liq bo'lgan 3 ta jarayondan iborat: virusning qon tomirlar endoteliyasiga sitopatik shikastlovchi ta'siri, "sitokinli shtorm" – Villebrand omillarining ajralib chiqishi, natijada qon ivish tizimining ichki hamda tashqi yo'nalishlarining faollashuvini stimullanishi, hamda mayda qon

tomirlarning shikastlanishi bilan tizimli vaskulitning yuzaga kelishi [23].

Xulosa. Yuqorida keltirilgan ma'lumotlardan kelib chiqqan holda xulosa tariqasida shuni ta'kidlash mumkin, koronavirus infeksiyasi sababli gospitalizatsiya qilingan bemorlarda D-dimer, fibrinogen, trombositlar soni va prothrombin vaqtini nazorat qilib borish ushbu bemorlar uchun prognostic kriteriy sifatida xizmat qilishi mumkin. Gemostaz tizimidagi buzilishlarni va trombotik asoratlar (koronavirus infeksiyasi bilan infitsirlangan bemorlar orasida tromboembolik asoratlar 27% dan 69% gacha holatlarda kuzatilishi mumkin) yoki gemorragik asoratlar xavfini aniqlash uchun, shuningdek, mikrosirkulyator qon aylanish tizimida trombofiliya yoki poliorgan yetishmovchiligi rivojlanishi xavfini oldindan aniqlash maqsadida D-dimer, fibrinogen, trombositlar soni, PV, EChT, C-reaktiv oqsil, laktatdehidrogenaza, triglitseridlar, ferritin kabi ko'rsatkichlarni nazorat qilib borish muhim ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi. Ushbu holatlarning asosiy va mavjud davosi hamda asoratlarning oldini olish uchun xizmat qiluvchi asosiy vosita bo'lib, past molekulyar geparinlar hisoblanadi.

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